

Applications of Forensic Medicine and Science for Insurance Purposes-A Broad Overview

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ABSTRACT: Forensic medicine and science are scientific disciplines where scientific (and medical) knowledge is applied to arrive at justice. They fundamentally assist the legal system (civil and criminal justice system) in a country by providing expert opinions to courts regarding medical and scientific matters beyond the comprehension of the legal fraternity. Likewise, these disciplines could extend their assistance in the field of insurance when certain issues arise which may seem contradicting with the accepted principles of insurance or with the terms and conditions of the policy. Insurance is a legal contract between the insurer (the insurance company) and the insured where the insurer undertakes the risk on behalf of the insured and agrees to provide financial protection against potential losses, damages or liabilities in exchange of a premium paid by the insured. An insurance policy is a detailed document comprising of declarations, agreement, exclusions, conditions, definitions and endorsements. Insurance may take many different forms including life, health, automobile, property, disability, travel and business. This article briefly explains the applications of forensic medicine and science in certain important areas of insurance.

KEYWORDS: insurance, applications of forensic medicine, contract, forensic science, legal system

INTRODUCTION

Relevance of forensic medicine and science in day-to-day civil and criminal matters

Forensic Medicine is the science as well as the art of application of medical knowledge, skills (and also to a certain extent, the attitudes) towards assist the courts in the execution of the justice. It is invariably the widest branch of medicine where rapidly growing medical knowledge in all aspects of human life (both in the living and the dead) including anatomy, pathology, physiology, general medicine, surgery, psychiatry, paediatrics, gynaecology, biochemistry, neurology and any other sub-specialty of medicine, is scientifically utilized to methodically assist the courts in an evidence-based manner, to draw their own inferences. Though it does not play an advocacy or advisory role upon the courts, in countries with developed and well-established legal systems in the world, it is unanimously and undoubtedly accepted across the globe that the assistance rendered by Forensics/Criminalistics is essential for the proper functioning of the legal system whose final and supreme goal is to achieve justice within the existing legal framework.

Forensic Medicine deals with the living as well as the dead. As such, it has two major subdivisions as Clinical Forensic Medicine and Forensic Pathology.

Clinical Forensic Medicine deals with the medico-legal issues of the living. The clientele of clinical forensic medicine covers the widest imaginable spectrum in human life though the bulk includes accidents (road traffic, railway, aviation, navigational, industrial, occupational, domestic etc.), assaults (with hands and feet without using weapons, using blunt or sharp weapons, firearms, explosives, corrosives such as acids and alkali, electricity etc.), sexual offences, child abuse, domestic violence, use of alcohol, abuse of recreational/dangerous/prohibited drugs, issues related to traffic medicine, issues related to torture/battering in custody/human rights violations, establishing human identity (for civil and criminal purposes), international war crimes, care for the detainees/custody medicine, refugee medicine, issues related to asylum seekers, mental health issues (fitness to plead, testamentary capacity, testimonial capacity, issues related to insanity and unsoundness of mind etc.) and so on and so forth.

Forensic Pathology deals with the medico-legal issues of the dead. Medico-legal issues are the questions/issues/problems the Judicial Medical Officer will have to find answers to when investigating a particular scenario. These questions will be posed to him by different interested parties including the Judge, the Jury, the defence lawyers, the prosecution lawyers, the relatives of the deceased, the interested general public, the media, the police and other stakeholders of the criminal investigations and the national and international organizations/agencies including human rights organizations. When dealing with the dead, the range extends

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across a very broad area from a single identified fresh body lying on a hospital bed died due to a known illness to charred, dismembered and fragmented human remains comingled with animal remains scattered over a few hectares of a thick forest following a mid-air explosion of an aircraft due to terrorist activity. The death variation may also include a cadaver of a new-born baby partially eaten up by animals abandoned in a dumpster, a skeletal remain recovered from an abandoned well or a toilet pit, an obviously extra-judicial execution in the form of a mass grave and even natural disasters such as Tsunami, floods or avalanche of soil in a gem pit. The medico-legal issues will include the establishment of the identity of the deceased. In forensic medicine, the identity essentially has two parts: the general identity (which includes age, sex, race and stature) and the specific identity (identification of the person by name out of many hundreds or even thousands of those who fulfil the same general identity criteria). Establishing the cause of death is another important medico-legal issue. The cause of death is the proximate physiological/pathological process which leads to the death of the individual. It should be stated according to the WHO format as far as possible. For the same cause of death, there could be several mechanisms operating inside the body. For example, the cause of death could be 'Drowning' while six or even seven mechanisms either alone or in combination could operate with in the body to bring about a death due to drowning (and these may include: asphyxia, oedema aquosum, emphysema aquosum, haemo concentration, haemo dilution, vagal inhibition and hypothermia). Apart from the cause of death and the mechanism of death, another important issue is the circumstances of death. There are only four circumstances of death viz; natural, homicidal, suicidal or accidental. For the same cause of death there could be possibilities of any one or more of the above circumstances. For example, a person walking along an 'Edanda' may slip his foot and fall in to water and drown, or he may purposefully with the intention of self-deliverance, jump in to water and drown himself or else somebody may push him in to water in the middle of the stream. In all of the above three scenarios, the cause of death is drowning while the circumstances are accidental, suicidal and homicidal respectively. The same is true for a cause of death following cranio-cerebral injuries due to discharge of a rifled firearm. The circumstances could be accidental (though rarely), or suicidal or more commonly homicidal. The time since death is another important medico-legal issue with lots of civil and criminal legal implications. With the passage of post-mortem interval, the accuracy of time (or the period) since death drops and the range will widen. Eventually, when it is a skeleton recovered from a body of water such as the basin of a large lake or from the depths of a river, or when it is a collection of human bones dug up from a mass grave, the period since death may extend from months to even years. Establishing the place of death becomes an issues when attempts are made for surreptitious disposal or when the person himself has made his way of escape after sustaining lethal injuries. Injury interpretation is equally important in clinical forensic medicine as well as in forensic pathology both for civil and criminal matters. The type of the injury (abrasion, contusion, laceration, cut, fracture, stab, burn etc.), the force (blunt, sharp or other), the type, nature and the features of the weapon, the contribution of injuries to death and or disability (which can be temporary or permanent and total or partial) and their contribution to loss of earning capacity (as in the cases of Workmen's Compensation), the distance, direction, disposition, number of assaults, reconstruction of the event, complications etc. are only some more important issues among numerous issues pertaining to injury interpretation. The deduction of the features of the weapon (the features of the knife or the firearm etc.) as well as assisting in the specific identification of the same are other important issues. Use of alcohol by the victim as well as by the perpetrators, the level of incapacitation, use of other substances of abuse and their identification and quantification, the presence or absence of associated crimes (such as rape in a murdered woman and robbery in a night watcher of a warehouse), the offences associated with pregnancy such as criminal abortion, the volitional activities (activities the person could have performed after sustaining lethal injuries but before succumbing to death), the period of survival, collection of trace materials and deducing the intension of assault (which is a relevant fact in many criminal cases based on mens rea) are some such medico-legal issues routinely popping up in forensic pathological investigations.

In Countries like Sri Lanka, India, Bangladesh, Pakistan as well as Switzerland, clinical forensic medicine and forensic pathology are both practiced by the same medical practitioner while in the UK, many parts of the continental Europe, North America (USA and Canada), Australia and New Zealand, clinical forensic medicine is practiced by forensic clinicians while forensic pathology is practiced by forensic pathologists. In Sri Lanka, the Judicial Medical Officers (Consultant JMOs in the Health Ministry) and the Professors, Senior Lecturers and Lecturers attached to the Departments of Forensic Medicine in state universities are considered as specialists in Forensic Medicine. Yet, a sizeable proportion of forensic/medicolegal work-load is still carried out by ordinary medical officer with MBBS or equivalent qualifications in the ministry of health who are in the calibers of district Medical Officer (DMO), MO-medicolegal and Senior Medical Officer (SMO) etc. According to the section 45 of the Evidence Ordinance, there is no legal barrier to accept such parties as 'medical experts'.

In addition to Forensic Medicine and Forensic Pathology, there are quite a number of allied sciences and disciplines which contribute towards forensic investigations.

Forensic Toxicology provides us with an insight of medico-legal aspects of poisoning/poisons and toxins as well as therapeutic and non-therapeutic drugs including ethyl alcohol, cannabis, cocaine, morphine, heroin, amphetamines and methamphetamines etc. It is immensely used in both civil and criminal matters pertaining to the living and the dead.

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Forensic Histopathology deals with pathological changes at tissue level. For example, for accurate dating of a heart attack (myocardial infarction) or a sub-arachnoid haemorrhage of the brain or even diagnosis of lobar pneumonia, tuberculosis, a maternal death due to amniotic fluid embolism or even evaluation of the consequences of a death following a 'medically mismanaged' surgery, one may heavily rely upon forensic histopathology. This is a rapidly growing discipline with involvement of enzyme and immune histo-chemistry and even more sophisticated molecular and genetic level studies.

Forensic Biochemistry helps us to understand the biochemical changes at the time of death. Though it is unfair by this vast subject to make an over simplification of its role and scope, what comes to our help to determine the blood glucose levels of a known diabetic patient at the time of his sudden death is forensic biochemistry. In the same way, serum electrolyte levels, vitreous humor ion levels, certain enzyme and hormone levels in the blood as well as the levels of therapeutic and non-therapeutic drug levels will be identified or back-calculated by using biochemical methods.

Forensic Anthropology is the study of human skeleton both in the living and the dead. Identification of the living is not-uncommonly assisted by forensic anthropologists. To study about anthropological characters of major human races (Caucasoid, Negroid and Mongoloid) and population dynamics are the main arena of forensic anthropologists working on the living. More importantly, in mass disaster situations, in case of missing persons, in exhumations of human bodies, in the excavations of archeological grave-yards as well as in the investigation of mass graves, extra-judicial executions and attempts of genocide, the contribution of forensic anthropology become extremely important and indispensable.

Forensic Odontology deals with the study of and interpretation of the findings of human teeth. This is equally significant in the identification of the living in clinical forensic medicine including bite-mark analysis of child abuse and sexual offences as well as in the identification of dead victims of fire where the facial and other external features are destroyed beyond recognition in case of grossly charred bodies where teeth being the most heat-resistant part of human body play a pivotal role in establishing the specific identity of the individual.

Forensic Entomology is the study of live and dead insects and their life stages to sort out a wide array of forensic issues mostly with reference to dead bodies which are surreptitiously disposed of with the intention of masking a secret homicide. There are well documented instances in the world including Sri Lanka where forensic odontology had played a vital role in establishing certain issues in murder trials.

Forensic Serology and DNA Technology deal with blood and body fluids. Serology includes study of different blood groups (there are more than 92 blood groups including ABO, Rhesus, Duffy, Kid, Kell, Lutheran, MNS and so on), Red Cell Antigens and Human Leucocyte Antigens. Prior to the invention of the DNA technology, these were the standard methods of human identification both the living and the dead including the cases of disputed paternity, disputed maternity, mixed-up babies, blackmailing for ransom, inheritance of property, identification of family trees/links, identification of assailants/suspects of sexual assaults, child abuse and murder, identification of the dead bodies, body parts, skeletal remains and so on. These methods were mostly used as a method of exclusion, certain well-known murder trials in the by-gone days in Sri Lanka stand out as instances where these methods were accepted as reliable means of establishing definitive identity of the victim as well as the suspect. Delivering almost all of these methods into forensic natural history museums, DNA technology (which is still widely known as 'DNA fingerprinting') has become the state-of-art technology in the present-day forensic investigations with ever-evolving new technologies including PCR and so on.

Computer/Cyber Forensics is another fast-evolving technology where from small-scale teller machine thefts to large-scale cyber-attacks and corporate crimes are handled. Tape/sound/video/photo authentication too comes under this which may be a matter of dispute in civil matters as well as in criminal defamation cases.

Forensic Psychiatry and Criminal Psychology are two closely related areas whose boundaries are obscure. As mentioned above, they mostly deal with issues related to the living. These issues could be highly contesting matters in civil cases including inheritance of property, compensation, financial remuneration/insurance claims, nullification of marriage, compulsory admission to mental hospitals, fitness to plead, acceptance of evidence, acceptance of testaments/wills and advanced directives etc. as well as in criminal cases which revolve around criminal responsibility/diminished responsibility and prediction of dangerousness. These disciplines may also be of assistance when deciding the vulnerability of detainees for false confessions and the admissibility of evidence given while in custody.

Forensic Science involves many diverse subjects including forensic chemistry, forensic physics, forensic biology, forensic geology, ballistics and explosive studies, study of questioned documents, study of finger prints, arson/fire studies etc. Most of these are dealt with in Sri Lanka by the Government Analyst's Department while Finger Prints and Questioned Documents are under the Police Department. Forensic chemistry deals with the establishment of chemical composition of substances. For example, in a hit-and-run accident the paint flakes found on the pedestrian may be matched with the paint of the suspect-vehicle.

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The matching of the chemical composition will also be of great assistance in civil cases of production of duplicate items and adulteration of commercial products such as therapeutic drugs, milk, grocery items and such other substances. Chemical analysis may also be of help to find out contamination of food/consumables with substances deleterious to human health. Forensic physics and biology may have innumerable uses in the modern world. For example, in the exportation/importation/smuggling of plant products/plants/animals/animal products and components of eco-systems; identification of these organisms and substances is done by forensic biology. Ivory, ornamental fishes, corals and 'Wallapatta' are just some examples. Authentication of hand writing, old deeds, wills and other instruments either originals or photocopies, is achieved by the section on questioned documents. The medico-legal relevance of finger prints in civil and criminal law in the country does not need over-emphasis.

Forensic Radiology is the use of X rays and other imaging techniques in the civil and criminal legal matters. Identification of the living and the dead with various imaging techniques including X rays, iris scans, CT and MRI are of common place today. Routine checks of fluoroscopy are done on passengers as well as their baggage in every air and naval port today. In the developed world, fluoroscopy and similar techniques are routinely used to scan long wheeled containers crossing the borders to detect illegal weapons and drugs.

If the manufacturer claims that the keys of the expensive piano you have recently bought are made of ivory and if you wish to differentiate whether it is true ivory (the tusks of the elephant) or whether they are made merely of the molar teeth of the elephant (which are relatively cheaper than ivory), *veterinary forensics* may play a key role in your assistance. This simple example elaborates that from before the birth to beyond the death of a person, for innumerable civil and criminal issues arising from time to time throughout our journey of life, different disciplines of forensic medicine come to our assistance.

Therefore, in the following discussion based on the applications of forensic medicine in the field of insurance, we need to take the content areas more broadly as the boundaries of forensic medicine merge with the other allied fields already mentioned above.

Medico-legally significant documents and expert medical witness

The judicial medical officers send MLEF (Medico-legal examination form) (Police 20) following medicolegal examination of patients. This document initially issued by the police in duplicate has two part -the police copy which is sent to the police by the JMO and the medical officer's copy which is retained by the doctor. If the matter appears before the Magistrate's court, the Magistrate will summon the doctor to send the Medico-legal Report (MLR) (H 1135) to the Magistrate's court which is the detailed report prepared by the doctor based on the information he had furnished on the doctor's copy of the MLEF at the time of examining the patient. When the matter comes up in the High Court following a non-summary proceeding at the Magistrate's Court, this MLR becomes an important documentary evidence upon which the doctor may be summoned to give oral evidence. While giving oral evidence any matter related to the patient may be asked and clarified from the JMO by the Judge, Jury, state counsel or the defence counsel. A copy of the MLR could be obtained by the defence from the courts. Insurance companies too can ask for the MLR or a free-style report from the doctor. The doctor can charge a reasonable fee and issue the report to the insurance companies with the consent of the patient. If a civil case is instituted in the District Court, the MLR or a free style report could be sent to the District Court too. The doctor can charge a reasonable fee and appear before the District Court. Defence medicolegal (forensic) practice both in the High Court and in the District Court is not yet well established in Sri Lanka, compared to the Western world and Australia. In highly contestable civil and criminal cases, there are instances where defense forensic pathologists have appeared from time to time.

Basic principles of insurance

It is the common knowledge of a legal personnel that insurance is a contract between two parties, the insurer and the insured, based on seven basic principles. These include the utmost good faith (*ubarima fide*), proximate cause (*causa proxima*), insurable interest, indemnity, subrogation, contribution and loss minimization. The utmost good faith includes transparency by both parties. In other words, both the insurer and the insured should disclose clear and accurate information regarding the contract without hiding relevant pieces of information. The principle of proximate cause is applicable when the loss could be due to more than one possibilities. The insurance will be paid only if the nearest cause for the damage is covered by the policy. The insured must possess an insurable interest in the object, property or the person covered by the policy. In other words, such property should have some financial benefit on the insured and destruction of the same should lead to a financial loss within the boundaries of law. The principle of indemnity implies that only the losses are recovered by insurance leading no room for 'unjust enrichment'. This principle assures that the insured is set back at the same financial position he had been prior to the financial loss but not at any higher (or lower) level. Under the principle of subrogation, once the insured is compensated by the insurer, for the losses incurred to the insured by a third party, the insurer owns a right to claim the amount of loss from such third party. The principle of contribution has a similar objective to the principle of indemnity. When a property (but not life) is insured under several insurance companies, the overall claim obtained from different companies should not exceed the actual loss. This principle also allows one insurance company to claim proportionate amounts from other insurance companies, if the total claim had been paid by a single company when the property has been insured with several companies for the same loss. The principle of loss minimization prevents the owner of the property from becoming negligent or irresponsible about his property simply because it has already been

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insured. In other words, even if the property is insured against a particular risk or a hazard, the owner should take appropriate measures to minimize such risk from becoming an actual loss.

The light of forensic medicine and science could be of immense assistance to clear the darkness on certain twilight zones associated with above principles. In other words, both the insured as well as the insurer may seek scientific assistance when confronted with issues intertwined with the above seven principles of insurance. Several such major areas will be discussed below.

DISCUSSION

Elaborations with some case examples:

1. Cause of death

For a death occurring in the ward which does not need an inquest, the cause of death is written according to the WHO format on the Declaration of Death Form (B 33) by the house officer. This goes to the Death Certificate when it is issued by the Births and Deaths Registrar. If an inquest is requested (in case of deaths where the cause of death is not known, all unnatural deaths, deaths due to suspicious circumstances, deaths due to criminal circumstances, deaths due to animals, deaths due to machinery, tetanus, rabies, deaths in custody, alleged medical negligence, certain statutory types of deaths such as Dengue, infant deaths and maternal deaths) it will be conducted by the Magistrate or the Inquirer in to Sudden Deaths (ISD) according to the provisions laid down from Sec. 369 to Sec. 373 of the Criminal Procedure Code. The house officer can mention the probable cause of death in the bead head ticket (BHT) to enable the ISD or the Magistrate to arrive at an apparent cause of death. If the ISD or the Magistrate decides that the death needs further scientific investigations, he will call upon a government medical officer to conduct a post-mortem examination, which is the final scientific investigation into a death. With the dissection alone or with the routine and ancillary investigations (as mentioned above) the JMO will delineate the cause of death. If the JMO cannot arrive at a cause of death, he will keep the autopsy as 'under investigation' and this will mandate the ISD or the magistrate to give an 'open verdict' at the inquest.^[1]

According to the WHO format, the cause of death (where possible) should be stated as a series of interconnected events. They include immediate cause of death (1A), antecedent/underlying cause/causes of death (1B, 1C, 1D etc.) and the Contributory causes (2)

For example:

PART I.

(Enter the chain of events-diseases, injuries, or complications-that directly caused the death. DO NOT enter terminal events such as cardiac arrest, respiratory arrest or ventricular fibrillation without showing the origin or the etiology.)

1a. IMMEDIATE CAUSE (Final disease or condition resulting in death)

1b. 1c. 1d. etc. UNDERLYING CAUSES (Sequentially list conditions leading to the immediate cause of death)

PART 2. CONTRIBUTORY CAUSES

Example:

Part 1:

1a. Rupture of myocardium

1b. Acute myocardial infarction

1c. Coronary artery thrombosis

1d. Atherosclerotic coronary artery disease

PART 2. Diabetes, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, smoking

- If the cause of death is stated meticulously according to the above format, it will rule-out any uncertainty regarding the breach of the 'utmost good faith' (*uberrima fide*) since *whether all the conditions the person was suffering from*, which may have some connection with his death, *had been disclosed or not*, could be easily found out.
- Yet, in a considerable number of deaths, which are not subjected to a postmortem examination (and are thus released from the ward with a B 33 form or only after an inquest) only a single cause of death or an apparent cause of death may be given. This will sometimes be unfair by the deceased as some of the conditions which he was actually suffering from will not be covered and thus will pose problems in the claiming of insurance.
- The client may at times be genuinely unaware of his own pathological conditions such as the level of coronary artery obstruction, myocardial fibrosis, cirrhosis of the liver, early stages of renal failure or even consolidations of the lungs, as these may in their early and moderate stages, be totally symptomless. Yet, when the same conditions are exposed during the autopsy/postmortem examination in the form of underlying or contributory causes of death, this may pose an unfair situation for the deceased as the insurance company may decline the claim based on violation of the utmost good faith.
- On the other hand, if the claimant had willfully concealed the above situations at the time of enrolling himself with the insurance scheme, such conditions may be disclosed during the autopsy examination.

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- Certain pathological conditions are extremely difficult to be established at autopsy. These may lead to negative autopsies where a definitive cause of death cannot be given. Functional abnormalities such as cardiac arrhythmias, sudden unexpected death in Epilepsy (SUDEP), snakebites, electrocution, electrolyte abnormalities, cardiac ion channelopathies, certain poisonings and some anaphylactic conditions etc. may fall into this category. In these circumstances too, it may pose a dilemma in insurance claims.
- Certain conditions such as different types of cancers, prostatomegaly, ovarian tumors and even age-related neurological conditions may be incidentally found during the autopsy. ^{[2] [3]}

2. Circumstances of death

As mentioned in the initial part of this discussion, for the same cause of death, there may be different circumstances such as natural, accidental, homicidal or suicidal. Clinical forensic medicine as well as forensic pathology including scene examination, play a significant role in the establishment of (or exclusion of) circumstances of death or injury. This has a direct relevance in civil as well as criminal cases. This is equally true in the field of insurance. ^[4]

A death due to road traffic incident (including car crashes), a railway tract incident, fall off a high-rise building, a body recovered from water, a firearm death, hanging, poisoning etc. could well be an accident, suicide or a homicide. Though establishing the circumstances in the above scenarios is rather difficult in the practical context, an experienced forensic pathologist together with the assistance of the police and the scene of crime officers, could almost always achieve it. A classic example from the recent past is the case where the husband had set fire to the mattress while the wife and two children were asleep. The police officers of the crime division as well as the scene of crime officers initially thought that this was an accidental fire and they were deliberately misled by the grief-stricken husband who was lamenting aloud. Consultant pathologist was able to confirm the ante-mortem nature of the burns on two victims and the post-mortem nature of the burns on the other victim and that the circumstances was in keeping with homicide. Upon questioning, the husband admitted the fabrications made by him at the scene and the 'cooked-up' nature of his story. Historically, in the famous 'Brides in the bath' case Mr. George Smith was found guilty of serial murder of his wives and was sentenced to death in 1915 at the Old Bailey London. He pretended that his wife had drowned in the bathtub and after the 'accident', claimed the insured money and then approached another rich widow who had been heavily insured. The suspicion was aroused by an accounts clerk in an insurance company as to how all of his wives could die following 'drowning' in the bathtub.

In clinical forensic medicine too, establishing circumstances will be of great significance. Some will voluntarily claim that injuries they suffered are due to accidental circumstances while actually the wounds had been inflicted in homicidal circumstances. This is done in fear of antagonizing underworld gang rivals. In case of physical child abuse, the perpetrators may claim that the injuries are due to accidental circumstance. Some others may cause self-inflicted injuries on hands, face, chest etc. or injuries will be inflicted by a 'friendly hand' and incriminate an innocent party for assault or sexual advance. An unsuspecting employee or security personnel will do the same to rob the daily collection or a bank or a warehouse. They will organize the robbery or theft and will claim that they were assaulted by the robbers and present with 'self-inflicted' injuries, which are easily distinguished from those due to an actual altercation. The same will be practiced to claim insurance of theft, robbery and arson. However, this forensic form of 'malingering' can easily be identified by an experienced forensic practitioner.

3. Time since death

This is invariably an important issue in criminal cases.

- In insurance matters, the date of origin of the disease condition or the pathology may be well before the expiry of the policy. Nevertheless, he may die of the same condition soon after the expiry of the policy and in this situation; forensic pathology will be of assistance to find out the date/time of origin of the condition. For example, a person may develop a sub-dural haemorrhage several days prior to the death. The expanding lesion in the brain may kill him two days after the expiry of the insurance policy. The forensic pathologist, with the help of histology (as mentioned above during the initial discussion) would be able to confirm that the origin of the illness had been prior to the expiry of the policy. ^[5]
- If two spouses or siblings die around the same time (one after the other), which is not an uncommon phenomenon, confirmation of the time of death and establishing who died first will be crucial in granting insurance as well as in the inheritance of property. This is especially true for those who are governed by certain special laws in Sri Lanka such as Muslim law and Kandian law. ^[6]

4. Dyadic suicides/homicide suicide combinations/suicide packs/religious fanatics

Dyadic suicides are homicide-suicide combinations. This is occasionally heard of between loving couples. One may kill the other and then kill himself. It is a homicide followed by a suicide. In countries pestered by extreme poverty, mothers committing suicide together with young children or after killing the offspring, is not unheard of. There are reported cases in the world where religious cults/fanatics commit mass suicides or mass killings. In such situations, if there were survivors, the issue arises as to whether they

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are innocent victims or active participants of suicide and homicide. The granting of insurance will depend on their role, which could be established by forensic pathology and clinical forensic examinations. ^{[7] [8]}

5. Period of survival

This means the time period a person could live after sustaining a fatal injury or a pathological condition. This may vary from just few seconds to several hours depending on the injuries, pathological condition and several other factors. This may occasionally be a materially significant issue in insurance claims, though it is invariably a very significant issue in criminal trials. During autopsy, the forensic pathologist would be able to give a fairly accurate 'gestimate' regarding the period of survival, though it could not be calculated or estimated with mathematical accuracy. ^{[9] [10]}

6. Volitional activities

Volitional activities are the activities a victim could indulge with, after sustaining fatal injuries but before succumbs to death. This is an important issue in criminal trials. In certain types of injuries, the volitional activities will be nil or minimal. For example, it is common knowledge that when the body is fragmented following a blast, volitional activities are impossible. Yet, in certain other seemingly serious injuries, the victim could be able to engage in a fare range of volitional activities. For example, if the bullet exited from a rifled weapon has gone through the frontal lobes of the brain (without serious vascular trauma), which are responsible for higher intellectual functions, such a victim could move himself for a reasonable distance, ask for help and even engage in such similar activities. On the other hand, if the same bullet has damaged the brainstem, which is responsible for spontaneous breathing and spontaneous beating of the heart, he will instantaneously die. The forensic pathologist is usually capable of deducing the level of volitional activities after completing the autopsy. Such issues may have relevance with insurance. ^[11]

7. Contributory factors and co-morbid factors

Contributory factors and co-morbid factors are of direct relevance in civil compensation and insurance claims. This is true in clinical forensic medicine as well as in forensic pathology. ^[12]

- A driver of a traffic accident, upon clinical forensic examination, may be found to be having compromised vision (visual acuity, colour vision and visual fields), poor coordination of muscles or poor hearing.
- During the autopsy of a pedestrian-victim of a fatal traffic accident, it may be found that he wears a glass-eye or a hearing aid or that he suffers from severe arthropathy hindering his free movement. All of these could well be contributory factors for the outcome of the event.
- An elderly driver of a three-wheeler may sustain a stroke (a cerebrovascular incident-CVA) and meet with a crash causing severe traumatic brain injury masking the stroke. During the autopsy, the CVA will not be found (though the root cause for the accident was the CVA) and the accident may be fully attributed to his sheer negligence. This will create an unfair situation for him in financial remuneration through insurance.
- An elderly person with moderate obstruction of the coronary arteries may suddenly suffer an unexpected cardiac arrhythmia. This can lead to an accident such as a traffic accident, industrial accident or a fall. During the autopsy, as arrhythmias are functional abnormalities and as such are not demonstrable and as moderate obstruction of coronary vessels is a very common age-related finding, a contributory cause for the accident would not be found. The obvious pathological condition would be over-looked due to its commonness.

8. Contributory negligence of the victim/employee and the employer

Contributory negligence of the victim/employee as well as the employer are important issues to be excluded while awarding financial remuneration in the form of insurance. ^{[13] [14]}

- The clinical examination of the live victims of industrial accidents, the autopsy of the dead victim of industrial accident as well as the scene visit to the work place and the place where the employee was found dead or injured, may solve the issues to a certain extent. Whether the personal protective equipment (PPE) have been provided, whether they were worn by the workman, whether the working environment was hazard-free and up to the standards explained in the contract, whether there were any injurious substances or faulty equipment making the premises a 'dangerous premises' under the law of delict, whether the workman had been engaged in the 'designated' job or anything outside his job description etc. could be found.
- A person may be chronically exposed to deleterious chemicals or carcinogenic substances such as asbestos, silica, coal dust, heavy metals, cyanide, arsenic, etc. during his employment and he will develop the adverse health effects such as cancers, chronic kidney disease etc. many years later, perhaps during his retirement or perhaps after changing the job or even after leaving the country. Both in the living as well as the dead, though the disease condition could be accurately diagnosed, establishing its co-relation with his previous employment would be a problem unless the patient develops the condition while still employed under the same employer. The matters will be further complicated if his second employment too has exposed him to similar hazards or if the employee too had some contributory factors such as not using protective gear and hazardous habits like heavy smoking etc.

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- If a person is exposed to a noxious gas, chemical or any such compound which could cause death or serious harm (such as cyanide gas, carbon monoxide, Sulphur dioxide, hydrogen sulphide, agrochemical/pesticide fumes, heavy metals etc.) during employment and if the postmortem biochemistry/toxicology report quantifies the amounts as sub-lethal (not enough to cause death) and if at the same time the deceased has other age-related conditions such as chronic kidney disease, chronic liver failure and ischaemic heart disease etc. the JMO will incorporate all the above findings in his postmortem report. Unless specifically asked from the JMO in his oral evidence, whether the sub-therapeutic or sub-lethal doses could kill a person with additional co-morbid factors, the insurance companies or the legal representatives for the interest of the employer will argue that the exposure was not adequate to cause the death.

9. Alcohol and drug issues

Ethyl alcohol is the commonest drug of abuse throughout the world. There are specific regulations regarding alcohol in Sri Lanka, Motor Traffic Act being only one such legislation. Recreational drugs of abuse (marijuana/cannabis, opium, heroin, morphine, other opioids, cocaine, amphetamines and methamphetamines etc.) are mainly governed by the amended 'Dangerous Drugs Ordinance'. A JMO may routinely examine clinical patients for consumption of alcohol and other drugs. He also may routinely encounter issues related to the same in forensic autopsy work/postmortem examinations.^[15]

- If a person is found to be drunk during working hours, it is an offence both in the state sector as well as in the private sector. Such employee may be produced before a JMO for clinical examination for alcohol with an MLEF issued by the police. After complete physical examination (specially aimed at determining the neurological impairment caused by alcohol) the JMO will indicate either of the three things in the relevant cages of the MLEF, ie: *none, breath smelling of liquor or under influence*. If the breath smelling alone was there without being under the influence, it is not an offence under the Road Traffic Act and such a motorist is not considered as an 'impaired driver'. He may be eligible to claim his insurance too, had he been met with a road traffic accident. But, if he was an employee found with 'breath smelling of liquor' (while being not 'under influence') still he would be considered as guilty and may even lose his job following disciplinary actions. The same employee, if had met with a workplace accident while 'breath smelling of liquor', will not be entitled to remuneration under Workmen's Compensation or any other insurance scheme.

Is this situation fair and just? What is medically meant by 'breath smelling'? Ethyl alcohol is an organic substance with no colour, taste, specific odor or a smell. The additional substances produced during natural fermentation (while preparation of liquor) or purposefully added by the manufacturer (which are known as 'congeners' or 'additives') only give different liquors different colours, tastes, smells and even different hangover effects. These substances are collectively known as 'additives' or 'congeners'. They only are responsible for the so called 'breath smell'. They are catabolized (broken down and eliminated) from the body in different pathways and ethyl alcohol is catabolized in the liver in a different pathway. So, the simple medical fact is that a person may not have even a trace ethyl alcohol in his blood but he may still be 'smelling' in his breath. In other words, breath smell is not an accurate indicator to categorically say that there is ethyl alcohol in his blood at that given moment. To make the matters more complicated, certain brands of liquors (such as White Diamond) does not have a smell. On the other hand, many medical conditions such as diabetic ketoacidosis, uraemia, renal failure etc. may give the patient's breath a 'specific ketotic smell' which is quite similar to the smell of liquor. It is the duty of the legal representatives of the patient to ask these questions from the medical expert witnesses during the cross examination if the justice for their client is to be met with. It is the understanding of the author that even some of the medical expert witnesses in Sri Lanka are not really aware of these facts. The only 'guarded opinion' an unbiased medical expert could provide if an examinee is smelling of breath (but not under the influence) is that ***'there is a very high probability that he might have consumed alcohol in the recent past'***, (but he should admit if questioned from him that he cannot say anything about the presence or absence of alcohol in the examinee's blood without going for a specific blood test.)

- Alcohol has an enormous individual variation in its clinical effects on a consumer. In other words, its physiological effects are (when the same amount of alcohol is ingested by different individuals at the same time) are extremely diverse and far from prediction. The most important factor is how habituated you are. If you are a regular drinker your body may adapt to alcohol and after some time you may tolerate large amounts without being under influence. There are many other factors affecting this situation which are beyond the scope of this discussion. In simple terms, one may be perfectly 'sober' even when his blood alcohol levels are around 180mg/dl while another person may be 'hopelessly drunk' while his alcohol levels are only around 60mg/dl. What does this tell us? Apart from the Motor Traffic Act, where the upper limit of blood alcohol is imposed as 80mg/dl to be in-charge of a motor vehicle on a public road, the levels of alcohol in a person's blood should not be strictly used to categorically say whether he was 'impaired' at that time or not. There is any way a crude generalization that with higher levels of blood alcohol, there is a higher chance of impairment and a person may be comatose and die around 450-500 mg of alcohol in 100ml of his blood. Yet, in much lower levels such as 150 or 200 etc., a JMO should not categorically say that the person could have been definitely impaired just because his blood alcohol levels are above 100 or so. This is quite unscientific and not evidence-based. Such dogmatic opinions are still given by some forensic pathologists in Sri Lanka and such 'opinions' should be considered as nothing less than 'forensic black magic' or 'voodoo'. The same is true in the so

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called 'back calculations' of the level of impairment at the time of death, looking at the Government Analyst's blood alcohol report. Just because the postmortem blood sample indicates that the blood alcohol level is 150mg/dl or so, while giving expert evidence, the JMO should not categorically say that the person would have been impaired/intoxicated/inebriated at the time of death. He should always consider the 'enormous individual variation' of alcohol in its effects on different individuals. But, he should be less hesitant to state about probability of impairment when alcohol levels are unacceptably high. ^[16]

- Lots of recreational drugs are being used in the complex society today and in most cases 'poly drug abuse' (cocktailing different drugs for better effects) is seen. Usually, alcohol and smoking are a part and parcel of this problem. There are 'multi-drug detecting kits' in almost all major forensic centres in Sri Lanka today and these kits can detect and semi quantify the amounts. It is simple to use and similar to the 'pregnancy detection dip stick' available in the pharmacy. Urine of the subject is used and this should always be collected in the presence of an authorized personnel. Mere presence of most of these drugs in blood itself is an offence in Sri Lanka. Yet, the legal representative of the aggrieved party should not hesitate to question the JMO about the 'window-period' of detection of the above drugs in these commercially prepared 'drug kits'. For example, marijuana or cannabis (in the form of 'tetra hydroxyl cannabinol') will be detected in urine by these kits using an enzymatic reaction even after some good two weeks following the last use. These kits only detect the presence of certain drugs, their by-products or metabolites in urine and does not necessarily say two things: firstly, whether the person is 'under the influence' of these drugs at the time of detection and secondly, when has he consumed the drugs. A person being penalized in different ways (including refusal of the insurance) for consuming a drug several days prior to the incident at question (at which time the person has no influence of the above drug) is not just and fair. Another important matter to be considered when interpreting the finding of multi-drug detection kits is the possibility of cross-reactions with commonly prescribed medications, leading to 'false-positive' results. There is increasing research evidence throughout the world to support this possibility. ^[17]

10. Injury interpretation

Injury interpretation (as discussed in the preliminary discussion above) is an important duty of the JMO both in the clinical patients as well as in the dead bodies subject to autopsy. Valuable information regarding the incident, features of the weapon, reconstruction of the event, intention, external injuries, internal organ damage, disability and many more could be obtained as forensic evidence. ^[18]

- A person was accused for culpable homicide amounting to murder under section 293 of the Penal Code as he has killed another person by assaulting him with a blunt object on his head. The JMO's postmortem report indicated severe cranio-cerebral injuries on the head of the victim due to a single blow with a blunt heavy object. The accused claimed that he had done it in self defence as the deceased had initiated the altercation who tried to kill him with a 'Manna knife' at the accused's boarding house. The astute defence counsel invited a reputed Forensic Pathologist to interpret the MLEF findings of the accused (the ordinary medical officer who had compiled the MLEF had migrated to Tasmania by the time the matter came up in the High Court) who appeared without a fee as he had realized the imminent injustice about to happen. The extensive defence injuries on the dominant hand of the accused in the form of cuts categorically indicated that he had been assaulted first with a heavy, long bladed sharp weapon and the type of the weapon was likely cause lethal injuries on his body. The accused was acquitted. Similar injury interpretations could be used in insurance purposes too to prove that the party claiming the life insurance is not the one who initiated the brawl.
- A fall could be easily distinguished from an assault on the back of the head by injury examination.
- Timing of injury/dating of injury is another important issue. A person may be assaulted on the head or sustain blunt force injury on the head following a motor vehicle crash and develop a sub-dural haemorrhage which expands slowly. Or, a person may sustain fractures following trauma, which will heal by callous formation. To corroborate the injuries to a particular traumatic event, dating/ageing/timing of injuries play a crucial role for which the forensic pathologist as well as the radiologist could be of assistance. It is not an uncommon incident, that a claimant of an insurance policy may attribute certain more serious injuries to a particular traumatic event which occurred after or before the said trauma.

11. Disability/Disfiguration/marriage problems/employability problems

In awarding financial remuneration, deciding upon the degree of disability (total or partial and permanent or temporary), loss of earning capacity (as given in the schedule 3 of the Workman's Compensation Act), level of disfiguration (which may amount to causation of Grievous Hurt under limb 'f' of section 311 of the penal code), reduction of employability etc. may be taken into consideration for all of which a JMO may be able to express a guarded opinion sometimes based on the finding of other relevant specialists such as surgeons, gynaecologists, eye surgeons, ENT surgeons, orofaciomaxillologists etc. ^{[19] [20]}

12. Estimation of Age/Human identity/Family lineage

Age estimation in the form of human identification is an important role in clinical forensic medicine. This will be important for those who do not have birth certificates and who have lost them due to various reasons etc. For those who do not have identity

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cards, the human identity may be established with DNA and other technology. Family linages, disputed maternity, disputed paternity and genetic relationship of ‘bastered’ children could be established or refuted all of which may have some relevance in inheritance of property and insurance claims. ^{[21] [22]}

13. Concussion and automatism

Concussion is transient paralysis of cerebral functions due to sudden blunt trauma to head. Grade I concussion could occur without losing consciousness. It recovers spontaneously with no macroscopically demonstrable brain lesions and is usually associated with retrograde amnesia-which means loss of memory of incidents occurred immediately prior to the blunt force on head. This can commonly occur in high velocity vehicle crashes as well as in certain contact-sports such as rugby, American football (‘fuddy’) and kick boxing. The victim may externally appear normal physically but his psychological functions may be abnormal for different periods of time depending on the severity of the impact. Such players are insured heavily and the spectators bet on teams and individual players in million dollar amounts. It is a very tricky and crucial decision to be taken by the sports medical specialist as to whether or not to allow such sportsmen to be sent back to the battle field. If the person behaves abnormally in the field, that may end up in serious damage to him and other players. Concussion, therefore is a very debatable topic in the field of insurance. Having known these facts, certain patients after blunt impact may malingering in the wards with ‘features of post-concussional symptoms’ and this is colloquially termed ‘compensation neurosis’ in clinical forensic practice. ^[23] Automatism is a condition where the person is not fully in charge of his five faculties (including motor functions) though he appears normal externally. This commonly happens in sleep walking (somnambulism) and also following head trauma (post-traumatic) and epilepsy (post-epileptic). If a person injures himself or others while functioning under automatism, he will be exempted from criminal responsibility. Awarding insurance claims under this condition is an ever-unsettled proposition. ^[24]

14. Fire investigations/Explosives/Firearms

Though this does not come directly under forensic medicine, such issues are dealt with in Forensic Science as mentioned above. Fire investigations are extremely important in the awarding of insurance for property damage as the fire could be initiated by the insured himself for obtaining the claim. Also there may be contributory negligence by the insured in the form of storage of fire accelerants/inflammable substances in the premises in an unauthorized manner or not maintaining the fire alarms, fire escapes (in almost all government buildings the final exit of the fire escape at the ground floor is locked to prevent squatters!) and faulty electric circuits etc. Death and damage to property of the inhabitants and workers of such premises should be accounted for by the owner of the premises if he has contributed by some means to the origin, spread and acceleration of the fire. The same principles will apply for firearms and explosives and storage of deleterious chemicals. ^[25]

15. Vicarious liability of the institution

Forensic medicine and forensic science (various branches of forensic science as described above) may play a handy role in deciding the vicarious liability of the institution/employer/any other party for the damages incurred to individuals. ^[26]

Though not practiced in the field of insurance in Sri Lanka, there are instances where the employees are collectively remunerated even if a single employee is subject to prejudice/mischief by an action of the administration/employer. For these purposes too, forensic reports may play a vital role. ^[27]

CONCLUSION

Clinical forensic medicine, forensic pathology and other allied fields of forensic science play a pivotal role in the field of insurance to arrive at justice in a scientific and evidence-based approach. This may help both parties-the insurer and the insured, to clarify their doubts and act lawfully claiming only what is just and fair.

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